

Complexation behaviour of (3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)alanine in some mixed coordinated systems : Equilibrium studies

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Abstract : Thermodynamic stability of complexes of Ni^{II} and Co^{II} with (3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)alanine (DOPA) and L-alanine, L-phenylalanine, L-aspartic acid and L-glutamic acid were investigated. Thermodynamic formation constants of these complexes were determined at three different ionic strengths at 20 ± 1°C and 30 ± 1 °C in aqueous medium under equimolar condition by subjecting experimental data to the computation applying SCOGS computer program.

Thermodynamic parameters for mixed coordinated systems were calculated by using van't Hoff isotherm, van't Hoff isochore and Gibb's Helmholtz equation. Species distribution is obtained for all ternary (biligand) systems. Complexation behaviour of ligands is discussed.

Keywords : Thermodynamic stability, mixed coordinated system.

Introduction

(3,4-Dihydroxyphenyl)alanine (DOPA) and dopamine are recognized as neurotransmitters¹. Alanine (Ala), phenylalanine (Phe), aspartic acid (Asp) and glutamic acid (Glu) are widely distributed in protein and also act as neurotransmitters². All these potential ligands are derivatives of alanine and likely to compete for metal ions *in vivo*³. Formation of mixed ligand complexes occurs commonly in biological fluids. The role of metal ions including Mg^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II} indicate the importance of mixed ligand complexes in the activation of enzymes in biological process⁴.

The possibility of formation of mixed-ligand complexes in biological liquids has promoted equilibrium studies on mixed-ligand complexes and species distribution of various nutrient and toxic metal ion complexes⁵⁻¹². In this view equilibrium studies were carried out on mixed ligand systems of (3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)alanine with some toxic and nutrient metal ions such as Pb^{II}, Hg^{II}, Cd^{II}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II} etc. Present paper deals with the stability and speciation of Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes.

Cobalt, in small amount, is essential to living organisms including human being. Cobalt is a central component of the vitamin cobalamine or vitamin B-12. Nickel

is contained in many enzymes and both these metals are counted as essential elements for human being¹³⁻¹⁵.

Results and discussion

The coordination behaviour of ligands was predicted by examining titration curves, using the method of Carey and Martell¹⁶. Analysis of M^{II}-DOPA-Ala/Phe systems reveals that the two ligands are coordinated to metal ion simultaneously in a single step. This fact is known by examining the titration curves (Fig. 1). It is observed that the mixed ligand curve (curve 5) shows lowering in pH as compared to metal-ligand titration curve (curves 2 and 4) in the initial stage.

However for M^{II}-DOPA-Asp/Glu systems, it is concluded that the two ligands are coordinated to metal ion in two distinct steps. Aspartic acid/glutamic acid coordinates in the first step and DOPA gets coordinated to the newly formed metal complex in the second step. This may be apparently understood by examining the titration curves (Fig. 2). The mixed ligand titration curve (curve 5) runs superimposed on metal-Asp/Glu titration curve (curve 2) upto pH ≈ 6.0. It gets shifted towards right hand side above this pH, thereby indicating the formation of mixed ligand complex.

Fig. 1. pH vs 'a' curves for Co^{II}-DOPA-Phe (1 : 1 : 1) system at 20 ± 1 °C ($\mu = 0.10 M$ (NaNO₃)).

Fig. 2. pH vs 'a' curves for Co^{II}-DOPA-Asp (1 : 1 : 1) system at 20 ± 1 °C ($\mu = 0.10 M$ (NaNO₃)).

where, Curve 1 represents ligand 'A' (DOPA) titration curve.

Curve 2 represents ligand 'B' (Ala/Phe/Asp/Glu) titration curve.

Curve 3 represents metal-ligand 'A' (1 : 1) titration curve.

Curve 4 represents metal-ligand 'B' (1 : 1) titration curve.

Curve 5 represents mixed-ligand (1 : 1 : 1) titration curve

Curve 'T' represents theoretical composite curve.

It is predicted that DOPA changes its coordination sites from aminocarboxylate to pyrocatechol mode. This prediction is attributed to the buffer region in curves 3 and 5. This coordination behaviour of DOPA is well documented and supported by spectroscopic studies¹⁷. Hence, the calculations were confined below pH 8.5 to avoid errors due to formation of polymeric complex species at higher pH¹⁸.

The qualitative analysis of experimental data is supported by quantitative results. Computation of results was carried using algebraic method of Chaberek and Martell^{19,20} as modified by Dey *et al.*²¹ and refined by SCOGS computer program²²⁻²⁴. These values were plotted against $\sqrt{\mu}$ and extrapolated to zero ionic strength to obtain thermodynamic formation constants and are given in Tables 1 and 2. Important thermodynamic parameters

Table 1. Protonation/dissociation constants of ligands ($\log \beta_{\mu \rightarrow 0}$) and thermodynamic formation constants of binary complexes of cobalt(II) in equimolar systems

Parameter	Ligand									
	DOPA		Ala		Phe		Asp		Glu	
	20 °C	30 °C	20 °C	30 °C	20 °C	30 °C	20 °C	30 °C	20 °C	30 °C
$\log \beta_{HA}$	-	-	10.25	10.01	9.31	9.12	10.57	10.26	10.33	10.07
$\log \beta_{H_2A}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	15.05	14.69	14.90	14.54
pK_{H_3A}	8.88	8.79	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
pK_{H_2A}	10.01	9.86	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
$\log K_{MAH_2}$	4.05	4.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
$\log \beta_{MAH}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	13.40	13.03	13.12	12.81
$\log \beta_{MA}$	-	-	5.24	5.09	5.10	4.98	7.57	7.40	6.82	6.66
$\log K_{MAH}^M$	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.83	2.78	2.79	2.74

Thermodynamic formation constants were obtained by extrapolating the $\log \beta$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ plot to zero ionic strength.

Ala, Phe, Asp and Glu become the ligand 'B' in ternary systems.

Table 2. Thermodynamic parameters of diprotonated M^{II} -DOPA-ligand 'B' ternary complexes in equimolar systems

System	20 °C		30 °C		$-\Delta H^\circ$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta S^\circ$ (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
	$\log K_{\mu \rightarrow 0}$	$-\Delta G^\circ$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$\log K_{\mu \rightarrow 0}$	$-\Delta G^\circ$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)		
Ni ^{II} -DOPA-Ala	11.08	62.18	10.82	62.80	43.95	62.19
Ni ^{II} -DOPA-Phe	9.94	55.77	9.70	56.28	40.97	50.53
Ni ^{II} -DOPA-Asp	12.99	72.88	12.76	74.01	39.79	112.92
Ni ^{II} -DOPA-Glu	12.10	67.86	11.87	68.84	39.36	97.27
Co ^{II} -DOPA-Ala	9.53	53.47	9.31	53.99	38.39	51.46
Co ^{II} -DOPA-Phe	8.87	49.45	8.65	50.18	37.01	43.49
Co ^{II} -DOPA-Asp	11.82	66.30	11.60	67.30	36.98	100.06
Co ^{II} -DOPA-Glu	11.03	61.88	10.84	62.91	31.83	102.59

like, ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° values for ternary complexes are also shown in Table 2. Speciation curves are given in Figs. 3–10. Figs. 3–6 show that above pH 6.0 metal interacts with both the ligands simultaneously resulting in monoligand and mixed ligand complexes. Mixed ligand

complexes come in existence above pH 6.5 and concentrations of binary and ternary complexes (MAH_2 , MB and $MABH_2$; where, ligand A = DOPA and ligand B = Ala/Phe) increase up to pH \approx 8.0. Above pH 8.0 concentrations of binary complexes decrease and that of ternary

Fig. 3. Speciation curves for Ni^{II}-DOPA-Ala (1 : 1 : 1) system at 20 ± 1 °C ($\mu = 0.10 M$ ($NaNO_3$)).

Fig. 4. Speciation curves for Ni^{II}-DOPA-Phe (1 : 1 : 1) system at 20 ± 1 °C ($\mu = 0.10 M$ ($NaNO_3$)).

Fig. 5. Speciation curves for Co^{II}-DOPA-Ala (1 : 1 : 1) system at 20 ± 1 °C ($\mu = 0.10 M$ ($NaNO_3$)).

Fig. 6. Speciation curves for Co^{II}-DOPA-Phe (1 : 1 : 1) system at 20 ± 1 °C ($\mu = 0.10 M$ ($NaNO_3$)).

where, Curve 1 : [M]; 2 : $[MAH_2]$; 3 : [MB]; 4 : $[MABH_2]$.

Fig. 7. Speciation curves for Ni^{II}-DOPA-Asp (1 : 1 : 1) system at 20 ± 1 °C (μ = 0.10 M (NaNO₃)).

Fig. 8. Speciation curves for Ni^{II}-DOPA-Glu (1 : 1 : 1) system at 20 ± 1 °C (μ = 0.10 M (NaNO₃)).

Fig. 9. Speciation curves for Co^{II}-DOPA-Asp (1 : 1 : 1) system at 20 ± 1 °C (μ = 0.10 M (NaNO₃)).

Fig. 10. Speciation curves for Co^{II}-DOPA-Glu (1 : 1 : 1) system at 20 ± 1 °C (μ = 0.10 M (NaNO₃)).

where, Curve 1 : [M]; 2 : [MBH]; 3 : [MB]; 4 : [MAH₂]; 5 : [MABH₂].

complex increases. These curves show that percentage of MAH₂ is comparable for M^{II}-DOPA-Ala and M^{II}-DOPA-Phe systems while that of MB is higher in latter system. In case of MABH₂ complex the order is reversed. This is because of electron withdrawing tendency of phenyl ring in phenylalanine and repulsion between bulky side groups of two ligands.

Percentage distribution (Figs. 7–10) of metal in M^{II}-DOPA-Asp/Glu systems shows formation of MBH (where, ligand B = Asp/Glu) complex up to pH 5.0. Afterwards, the concentration of MBH decreases and that of MB increases and its maximum formation is observed near pH 7.0. Concentration of MAH₂ is found to be very low. Diprotonated MABH₂ ternary complex is seen to be formed in the solution above pH 6.5 and its concentration is quite appreciable. Possible equilibria for complexation of these systems are given in Schemes 1 and 2.

Scheme 1. Simultaneous complexation equilibria for M^{II}-DOPA-Ala/Phe systems.

The calculations were confined below pH 8.5 to avoid errors due to formation of polymeric complex species at higher pH²⁴.

Results obtained for all these systems show that stability of complexes of alanine and phenylalanine is comparable and complexes of alanine are found to be more stable. This fact can be explained on account of structure of these ligands. The only difference in the structures of

(Charges have been omitted for the sake of simplicity)

Scheme 2. Stepwise complexation equilibria for M^{II} -DOPA-Asp/Glu systems.

these ligands is the presence of electron withdrawing phenyl group in phenylalanine, which reduces the stability of its complexes. Likewise aspartic acid and glutamic acid have similar structures with two carboxylic groups, which makes complexes of these ligands more stable than those of alanine and phenylalanine. Further, the values of ΔG° is comparatively more negative for the systems of aspartic acid, which is attributed to the presence of additional $-\text{CH}_2-$ group in the side chain of glutamic acid.

This equilibrium analysis of mixed coordinated systems of DOPA can serve as important data in understanding the behaviour of DOPA as therapeutic drug in treatment of Parkinson's disease and side effects associated with it.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of highest purity Merck/Aldrich products. Solutions were prepared by standard method in deionised water having pH \approx 6.8.

The protonation and coordination equilibria were investigated by pH-metric titrations in aqueous medium ($\mu = 0.05 M, 0.10 M, 0.15 M$ (NaNO_3)) at $20 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and $30 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ using an Elico digital pH-meter model LI-127 with ATC probe and combined electrode type (CL-51B-Glass Body; range 0–14 pH unit; 0–100 $^\circ\text{C}$ automatic/manual) with accuracy ± 0.01 . Following sets of titration mixtures were prepared, keeping total volume 50 mL and titrated against 0.10 M NaOH solution :

- (i) Acid titration : HNO_3 ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$)
- (ii) Proton-ligand 'A' system : HNO_3 ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + ligand 'A' ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$)
- (iii) Metal-ligand 'A' (1 : 1) binary system : HNO_3 ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + metal nitrate ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + ligand 'A' ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$)

- (iv) Proton-ligand 'B' system : HNO_3 ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + ligand 'B' ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$)
- (v) Metal-ligand 'B' (1 : 1) binary system : HNO_3 ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + metal nitrate ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + ligand 'B' ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$)
- (vi) Metal-ligand 'A'-ligand 'B' (1 : 1 : 1) ternary system : HNO_3 ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + metal nitrate ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + ligand 'A' ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + ligand 'B' ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$)

where, ligand 'A' = (3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)alanine and ligand 'B' = L-alanine/L-phenylalanine/L-aspartic acid/L-glutamic acid.

Titration curves obtained by plotting pH against ' a ' (where, ' a ' is the moles of alkali added per mole of metal/ligand). Representative curves are shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

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References

1. D. Balasubramanian, "High Speed Knockout in the Brain", *Everyman's Science*, April-May, 2006, XLI, 68.
2. C. U. M. Smith, "Elements of Molecular Biology", 2nd ed., John Wiley & Sons, Chichester, 324.
3. I. Bertini, H. B. Gray, S. J. Lippard and J. S. Valentine, Viva Books Private Ltd., New Delhi, 1998.
4. W. Kaim and B. Schwederski, "Bioinorganic Chemistry", New York, 1994.
5. T. Jakusch, S. Marcão, L. Rodrigues, I. Correia, J. C. Pessoa and T. Kiss, *Dalton Trans.*, 2005, 3072.
6. G. Goswami, R. Ahuja and K. Dwivedi, *Int. J. Chem. Sci.*, 2006, 4, 381.
7. M. J. Zaworotko, H. H. Hammud, I. Abbas, V. Kravtsov and M. S. Masoud, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2006, 59, 65.
8. V. Golovanov, *J. Anal. Chem.*, 2006, 61, 369.
9. İ. Erden, N. Demirhan and U. Avcıata, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2006, 45, 1395.
10. T. Kiss, K. Gajda-Schranz and P. F. Zatta, *Metal Ions Life Sci.*, 2006, 1, 371.
11. T. Kowalik-Jankowska, A. Rajewska, E. Jankowska and Z. Grzonka, *Dalton Trans.*, 2006, 5068.
12. T. Biver, D. Lombirdi, F. do-Secco, M. R. Tiné, M. Venturini, A. Bencini, A. Bianchi and Valtancoli, *Dalton Trans.*, 2006, 1524.
13. P. J. Thornalley, *Biochem. Soc. Trans.*, 2003, 31,

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1343.

14. R. K. Szilagy, P. A. Bryngelson, M. J. Maroney, B. Hedman, K. O. Hodgson and E. I. Solomon, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **126**, 3018.
15. G. Jaouen (ed.), "Bioorganometallics : Biomolecules, Labeling, Medicine", Wiley-VCH, Weinheim. 2006.
16. G. H. Carey and A. E. Martell, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 9895
17. R. K. Boggess and R. B. Martin, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **97**, 3076.
18. P. K. Bhattacharya and M. Vadapadapatri, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1989, 567
19. S. Chaberek and A. E. Martell, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 5052.
20. S. Chaberek and A. E. Martell, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 1477.
21. Ram Nayan and A. K. Dey, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, **14**, 892.
22. I. G. Sayce, *Talanta*, 1968, **15**, 1397.
23. I. G. Sayce, *Talanta*, 1971, **18**, 653.
24. I. G. Sayce and V. S. Sharma, *Talanta*, 1972, **19**, 831